

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B155
 Date: 04 Jan 2006
 Take Off 11:22:42
 Landing: 15:35:45
 Flight Time 4h13m03s

Campaign: Pre DABEX test
Operating Area: North Sea coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manger	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Cloud physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
7	Mission Scientist 2	Simon Osborne	Met Office
8	Mission Scientist 3	Ben Johnson	Met Office
9	Wet Neph (1)	Martin Glew	Met Office
10	Core Chem/CCM2	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
11	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
12	SWS (training)	Claire McConnell	Reading University
13	VACC 1	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
14	VACC 2	Barbara Brooks	Leeds University
15	Dogsbody	Stuart Heath	FAAM
16	Mission Scientist 4	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
17	CCM (training)	Joanne Green	Directflight
18			
19			

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b155

Date: 4 Jan 2006

Project: Pre DABEX test

Location: North Sea coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
103551		INU	-.13 kft	127	to nav 52' 04.36N 0' 37.48W
112242		T/O	-.11 kft	032	cranfield
112636		video	5.0 kft	064	power recycled to rh system
113051	122940	Run 1.0	7.0 kft	355	
113134		Heimann	7.0 kft	353	open / measure
113209		video	7.0 kft	346	#1 ffc, #2 ufc
113231		nev	7.0 kft	338	zeros
113253		BBR	7.0 kft	325	retract
113450		manouvrrre	7.0 kft	321	
113544		JW	7.0 kft	351	u/s
114014		HORACE	7.0 kft	353	drs check - satis
121701		Heimann	7.0 kft	353	cal
122652		HORACE	7.0 kft	348	reboot
122941	124429	Profile 1	7.0 - -.48 kft	347	50ft
123040		BBR	6.3 kft	352	extend
123253		5000'	4.3 kft	353	reduce to 500ft/min
123806		qnh	1.8 kft	351	1030
124023		P1	0.58 kft	350	interrupt, manouvre
124220		P1	0.56 kft	185	restarted
124429	124848	Profile 2	-.48 - 2.0 kft	185	50ft
124901		level	2.0 kft	195	2500'
125215	125504	Profile 3	2.0 - 0.57 kft	356	landing configuration
125505	125619	Profile 4	0.57 - 2.0 kft	356	climb away
125844	130408	Profile 5	2.2 - -.41 kft	196	
130119		P5	0.55 kft	196	interrupt 1000'
130153		video	0.56 kft	253	#3 ffc, #4 ufc
130216		P5	0.54 kft	256	restart
130608	131607	Run 2.0	-.41 - -.40 kft	099	100
130729		bbr	-.42 kft	099	retract
131818	132822	Run 2.1	-.41 - -.36 kft	259	100'
131852		Heimann	-.42 kft	256	cal
131902		nev	-.40 kft	255	zero
132955	133957	Run 3.0	0.03 - 0.01 kft	106	500'
134116	135117	Run 3.1	0.01 - 0.03 kft	282	500'
135236	141954	Profile 6	0.04 - 25.0 kft	107	
135253		P6	0.24 kft	106	500' to fl250
135420		BBR	1.3 kft	105	extend
135812		roc	4.1 kft	107	1000'
140835		P6	15.0 kft	086	interrupted, manouvre
141035		P6	15.0 kft	282	restart
142351	142934	Run 4.1	25.0 kft	119	142361
142615		nev	25.0 kft	119	zero
143153	143706	Run 4.2	25.0 kft	304	
143729	143901	Orbit 1	25.0 kft	355	360 start heading
143946	144114	Orbit 2	25.1 - 25.0 kft	045	060
144143	144310	Orbit 3	25.1 - 25.0 kft	082	100
144345	144518	Orbit 4	25.1 kft	150	140
144815		!	25.0 kft	151	end science - transit
152528		asps	8.8 kft	163	closed
153545		Land	-.09 kft	307	Cranfield
154133		INU	-.09 kft	307	52' 04.16N 0' 37.93W
154217		GPS	-.09 kft	307	52' 04.36N 0' 37.50W

B155 Track 04-JAN-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

Pre-DABEX clear skies test flying

Flight No: B155

Date: 4th January 2006

Trial objectives:

To test radiometers and aerosol sampling equipment that are essential to the DABEX campaign (Jan-Feb '06). These include: (1) wet neph, (2) BBRs, (3) ARIES, (4) SWS, (5) PCASP.

Location:

North Sea, off Newcastle.

Weather:

Ideally cloudless skies, stable anticyclonic conditions; advection of pollution over the area.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield.
2. Transit out to operating area at high level [20mins, tot=20mins]
3. Box pattern at FL250 with outside turns, 5 min legs, legs orientated into-, across-, down- and across- Sun; [25mins, tot=45mins].
4. Series of four orbits at FL250, bank angle to be 60deg [10mins, tot=55mins]
5. Profile descent to 50ft at rate of 1000ft/min above the boundary layer and 500ft/min within the boundary layer [30mins, tot=85mins]
6. Two reciprocal 10 min SLRs at 100ft orientated approx across Sun [25 mins, tot=110mins].
7. Profile ascent to 1000ft at rate of 500ft/min [5mins, tot=115mins].
8. Two reciprocal 10 min SLRs at 1000ft orientated approx across Sun [25 mins, tot=140mins].
9. Profile ascent to 2000ft at rate of 500ft/min [5mins, tot=145mins].
10. Two reciprocal 10 min SLRs at 2000ft orientated approx across Sun [25 mins, tot=170mins].
11. Profile ascent to FL250 at 500ft/min within the boundary layer and at 1000ft/min above this; [25mins, tot=195mins].
12. Transit back to base [20mins, tot=215mins]
13. Land at Cranfield.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.155**.....

 Date ...4th January 2006

Page1 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:00					T=6°C 1024 QNH.
11:20					T/O Crawfield.
11:30:51	R1	FL070			R1 start.
					8/8 Sc below - tops ~ 3000ft.
					Flight progressing to Newcastle.
					Not much pollution.
12:00					Wet neph leaking water.
12:09:00					Low levels of both CO (12 ppbv)
					and O ₃ (50 ppbv)
12:25:00					Clear below at ~ 12:25
12:29:41	R1 / P1	FL070 ↓			End R1 start P1 at 1000ft/min.
					Clear area to E of Firth of Forth.
					Some Ci above
					Still no signif pollution to 3500ft
12:40:23	Int P1				Interrupt at 1000ft.
12:42:20	Restart P1	1000ft ↓			500ft/min restart.
					Sea-state 1-2 no breaking waves, low PCASP concentrations
12:44:29	End P1 / Start P2	500ft ↑			~ 50 cm ⁻³ .
					Sc to East, Ci to west, some contrails.
12:48:48	End P2	2500ft			
12:50:30	Start P3	2500ft ↓			Flaps 24 - Undercarriage & flaps.
					'Missed approach' style descent to 1000ft. KIAS 130kts.

120
38

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**...155.....

Date ...4th January... 2006

Page2 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	End P2 St P5				Dirty climb to 2500ft.
12:58:44	St P5	2500ft	↓		1000 ft/min
13:02:19	Int P5	1000ft			
13:02:16	Restart P5	1000ft	↓		500ft/min
13:04:08	End P5	100ft			End P5.
13:06:08	St R2.0	100ft	→		.
13:08					CO increases from 100 → 160 ppbv
					Z-D confirms increase in aerosol
13:12					Sc above 7/8 half way through
13:16:07	GR2.0				Good run for wet-neph.
13:18:18	St R2.1	100ft	→		Sc above.
					Sc edge passed at 13:22:30
					V. little Ci above.
					Sea state 1.
	End R2.1				
13:29:55	St R3.0	500ft	→		13:35 going under 6/8 Sc.
					Wet nephelometer report is good.
13:39:57	End R3.0	500ft			Reposition onto reciprocal.
13:41:60	St R3.1	500ft	→		Sea surface albedo ~ 0.3.
					Good run at the end for SWS.
13:51:17	End R3.1				
13:52:53	P6	500ft↑			Start profile at ⁵⁰⁰ 1000ft/minute.
					Increase to 1000 ft/minute at 4000ft
140835	P6				interrupt
141035	P6				restart

↑

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 155

Date: 4/1/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:30:52																Start Run 1 @ FL070	
11:31:00	25	0.09	4														
11:33:00	25	0.09															
11:35:00	18	0.08			Noise												
11:37:00	15	0.10			Noise												
11:39:00	15	0.09			Noise												
11:41:00	15	0.08			Noise											Stop SID2 recording as Noise is high	
11:43:00	15	0.08			Noise												
11:45:00	16	0.08			Noise												
11:47:00	15	0.08			Noise												
11:49:00	13	0.08			Noise												
11:51:00	15	0.08			Noise												
11:53:00	14	0.08			Noise												
11:55:00	11	0.08			Noise												
11:57:00	13	0.08			Noise												
11:59:00	15	0.08			Noise												
12:01:00	16	0.08			Noise												
12:03:00	14	0.08			Noise												
12:05:00	25	0.08			Noise												
12:07:00	20	0.08			Noise												
12:09:00	30	0.08			Noise												
12:11:00	50	0.08			Noise												
12:13:00	55	0.08															
12:15:00	50	0.08															
12:17:00	50	0.08															
12:19:00	30	0.08			Noise												
12:21:00	30	0.08															
12:23:00	35	0.08			Noise												
12:25:00	35	0.08			Noise												
12:27:00	35	0.08			Noise												
12:29:41	30	0.08														End of Run 1 & Start Profile 1 from FL070	
12:30:52	30	0.08														FL060	
12:31:57	10	0.08														FL050	
12:33:28	17	0.08														FL040	
12:35:42	5	0.09		1												FL030	
12:37:42	25	0.10		15	3											FL020 SID 2 Recording on	
12:39:23	50	0.10		70	10											FL010	
12:44:30	60	0.10		80	10											End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2 @ 50'	
12:47:04	40	0.10		50	10											FL010	
12:48:50	10	0.11		10	3											End of Profile 2 @ 2500'	
12:52:16	12	0.12	5	10	2											Start of Profile 3 from 2500'	
12:54:08	50	0.11		60	8											FL010	
12:55:06	50	0.10		60	10											End of Profile 3 & Start Profile 4 @ 1000'	
12:56:30																End of Profile 4 @ 2500'	
12:58:44	10	0.11		5	1											Start Profile 5 @ 2500'	
13:00:11	45	0.10		70	10											FL010	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 155

Date: 4/1/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:04:10	200	0.08	5	90	10											End of Profile 5 @ 100'	
13:06:09																Start Run 2.1 @ 100'	
13:07:00	150	0.08		90	10												
13:09:00	550	0.08		90	10												
13:11:00	80	0.09		90	15												
13:13:00	40	0.11	6	70	10												
13:15:00	35	0.11		50	10												
13:16:09																End of Run 2.1	
13:18:20																Start Run 2.2 @ 100'	
13:19:00	35	0.11		60	8												
13:21:00	45	0.10		80	10												
13:23:00	400	0.08		80	15												
13:25:00	200	0.08		80	10												
13:27:00	120	0.09		80	10												
13:28:20																End of Run 2.2	
13:29:59																Start Run 3.1 @ 500'	
13:30:00	80	0.09	7	90	10												
13:32:00	140	0.08		90	10												
13:34:00	150	0.08		90	10												
13:36:00	60	0.09		80	10												
13:38:00	55	0.10		30	8												
13:39:59																End of Run 3.1	
13:41:18																Start Run 3.2 @ 500'	
13:42:00	55	0.10	8	60	10												
13:44:00	45	0.09		70	10												
13:46:00	100	0.09		90	10												
13:48:00	240	0.08		90	10												
13:50:00	110	0.08		Crash													
13:51:26																End of Run 3.2	
13:52:38	90	0.08	8		10											Start Profile 6 from 500'	
13:53:53	50	0.08			10											FL010	
13:54:59	10	0.08			2											FL020	
13:56:36	5	0.08	9	1												FL030	
13:58:12	20	0.08		1												FL040	
13:59:06	20	0.08														FL050	
14:00:00	35	0.08		1												FL060	
14:01:00	30	0.08		1												FL070	
14:01:46	125	0.09		1												FL080	
14:02:38	160	0.09		1												FL090	
14:03:34	13	0.08		1												FL100	
14:04:40	5	0.08		1												FL110	
14:05:31																FL120	
14:06:37	25	0.08														FL130	
14:07:34	15	0.08														FL140	
14:08:36	50	0.08														FL150	
14:11:40	20	0.09														FL160	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B155**Date:** 04/01/06

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown		
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Note the calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit		Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B155**Date:** 04/01/06

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	X	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	X	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	X	
4) Log on to FLOODS	X	
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	X	
6) In PVWAVE		Bad blocks = 0 Blocks read = 39000 Blocks written = 39000
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	X	
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat	X	
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat		
iii) exit	X	
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	X	
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	X	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat	X	
d) Comment string:	X	
e) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
f) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
g) Read 2DC: Y	X	
h) Read 2DP: Y	X	
i) Secondary data Y	X	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	X	
k) cmd.str: Y	X	
l) Auto time correction: N	X	
m) Full length secondary: N	x	Large number of output conversion errors whilst writing to B155_2DP_SEC.OUT ascii file; main output still ok, though
8) 2D image display and printing		This section is optional
Quick look at image blocks if required		
In PVWAVE		
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
j) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY		
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: 0 if unknown		
f) End time: 240000 if unknown		

Features to look for:

- 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)?
- 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals)
- 3)

<p>g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec</p>		
Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
<p>iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files</p>	<p>PMSDATA:</p>	<p>FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS</p>
<p>ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC</p>		
<p>Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter</p>		
<p>Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files</p>		
<p>9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data</p>		<p>If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end.</p>
<p>e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unknown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>Note the particle type</p>
<p>10) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' iii) exit</p>		
<p>11) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		
<p>12) CHECKS:</p>		
<p>i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?</p>		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B155**Date:** 04/01/06

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	X	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	X	Note the min size channel
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	Note the volume flow rate
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	X	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	X	
d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here	x	Bin 1 entered
e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec	x	1.8 cm ³ /sec (high!); value from recent calibration in the USA.
f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)	x	Zero
g) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
h) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
3) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!	X	
ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat' ,pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	X	
iii) exit	x	
4) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp	X	
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	x	Renamed to MFDB
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B155	Date	4/01/06		Opera tor(s)	Ian Rule	log page	of
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks		
				Vis	NIR			

0949						SWS checked ok, box temp = 18		
112240						T/o		
1128						Initialisation failure, cleared by restarting software		
113051	R1	FL70	Zen+6	200	500	Not recording initially		
121537						Start video, clear above, Sc below, box temp=12		
122941	R1/P1	FL70	Zen+6	200	500	End run start profile		
124023		1000'				Interrupt profile		
124220						Restart		
124430	P1/P2	50'	"	400	1000	End profile, start next profile		
124849	P2	2500'	"	"	"	End profile		
125216	P3	2500'	zen	"	"	Start profile		
125506	P3/P4	1500'	zen	"	"	End profile, start next		
1256	P4					End profile, box temp = 14		
125844	P5	2500	Zen+6	"	"	Start profile, box temp = 13		
130119	P5	1000'	"	"	"	Interrupt profile		
130216	P5	1000'	"	"	"	Restart		
130408		100'				End profile		
130608	R2.1	100'	"	"	"	Start run, mostly clear above, running under some Sc. Box temp=11, sun on window		
131607						End run		
131818	R2.2	100'	"	"	"	Start run, some cloud above, box temp=12, sun not on window		
132819		100'				End run		
132957	R3.1	500'	"	"	"	Start run		
133957						End run		
134117	R3.2	500'	"	"	"	Start run, box temp =12		
135117						End run		
135253	P6	500'	"	"	"	Start profile, box temp = 11		
142351	R4.1	FL250	"	"	"	End profile, start next (cross sun run)		
142934	R4.1					End run		
143153	R4.2	FL250	"	"	"	Start run, cross-sun		
143706	R4.2					End run		
143729	O1	FL250	"	"	"	Start orbit		
143901	O1	"	"	"	"	End orbit		
143946	O2	"	"	"	"	Start orbit, bank angle 50, orbit R		
144114	O2	"	"	"	"	End orbit		
144143	O3	"	"	"	"	Start orbit, bank angle 50, orbit R		
144310	O3	"	"	"	"	End orbit		
144345	O4	"	"	"	"	Start orbit, bank angle 48, orbit R		
144518	O4	"	"	"	"	End orbit		
144815		FL250	"	"	"	Transit home		
150000						Stop video, counter time=2:43:46		

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B155**.....

Date 04/01/2006

Operator's name: M. GLEW/S. OSBORNE

Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
	Pre-flight							Run for 30 mins with water in - nothing in trap
	R1A			dry 58%	dry 70%	post-dry 50%		Humidity 80%, wet neph 73%.
				All ok on computer startup - Dry Com port 1, wet com port 2.				
				Zeroed nephs pre-flight				
1130				wet neph cons ok just before (D)				
1135			9.5	53	82			pre dry 27%, post dry 32% Humidity 49%.
1136		FL070		wet Neph, Dry Neph				Zeroed. PCASP reading 15
				both wet + dry neph scattering around zero (tve, -ve a little)				
				Trap full 3/4 full soon after arrival at 7000'. Chiller not on. Tried to empty trap - think water went into wet neph as air rushed in. 1 finger water left. Trap stable after this.				
1245	P1	1000'	10.0	30%	65%			GF ~ 1.3 → 1.4 Chiller off, but fall of water at ~ cabin temp. large spikes on GF (2.9 → +7.0) !!!
				spikes when TAS decreased at start of "missed approach"				
1304	end	100'	10.0	36	62	↓	48	Trap OK, Chiller on, set to +5°C
1306	R2	100'	10.2	38	58	↓	+10.5	+6.7 at 13:10
1312	R2	100'	9.8	38	48	↓	T.S.3	
1314	R2	100'	10.0			↑		T _{Hzo} set to +10.0°C
1314	55						10.0	Now.
1316	50					↑		Set to 15°C = T _{Hzo}

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B.155**.....

Date 04/01/06.....

Operator's name: OSBURN/CLAW.....

Page 2 of 2.

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
132015	R2.2	100'	9.2	35	50			
1321	PUMP OFF, Trap drained, pump ON.							
132210	R2.2	100'	9.7	38%	52%	↑		Increase temp of H ₂ O to 20°C
132320	R2.2	100'	9.8	39%	55%		20.0°C	
132430						↑	25.0°C	Increase temp.
132650	R2.2	100'	9.7	35%	62%	↑	30.0°C	" " again.
133039	R3.1	500'	9.6	30%	72%			
133050	————— PUMP OFF & ON TO DRAIN TRAP.							
133230	R3.1	500'	9.4	34	75%	↑	35.0°C	→ set to.
133638	R3.1	500'	9.5	34%	84.5%	↑	37.0°C	Increase by 2°C only (under cloud also)
133930	R3.1	500'	9.4	32%	88%	↑	39.0°C	" " "
134020								PUMP OFF. TO DRAIN TRAP.
134037								PUMP ON. AGAIN
134160	R3.2	500'						Start Run on reciprocal -
134220						↑	41.0°C	Increase by 20°C only.
134320			9.8	31%	94%	→	41.0°C	Probably much more than desirable.
134440				34	94	↓	40.0°C	Decrease Temp to 10°C.
135215								PUMP OFF TO DRAIN.
135237			9.7	31%	80%	↓	15.0°C	" ON AGAIN. Lid dropping slowly.
~1358				20%	58%			DRAIN SYSTEM OF WATER.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 155**

Date: 4th January 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	N
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ JN02	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
“ JN02	Y	AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B155

Date: 4th January 2006

Instruments

1. SID 1 – working
2. PCASP – noisy at high alt
3. 2D-P noisy at high level
4. 2D-C noisy at high level
5. FSSSP ok
6. SID 2 working, some noise
7. ARIES not operated (removed)
8. MARSS not fitted
9. DEIMOS not fitted
10. JW zero pot is set to nearly full scale (fully clock), zero now stuck off scale (-ve) INSTRUMENT US
11. Neph; problem – cannot see data on HORACE
12. Printer locked up - required restarting
13. HORACE and FM PC crash ~12:19 required complete restart
14. Mission Scientist's pc ethernet cable becoming unreliable

Aircraft

Operated 'flight deck door closed'

Satcom H Calls

1 call by DFL to check out medilink test (satis) 2mins

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B155:

Log	Reason
De-brief	No De-brief was written for this Sortie.
Core Chemistry	No In Flight log provided
VACC	No log is taken/provided for VACC

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The Digital8 video recordings from this flight were not requested to be archived so have been reused.